

TULONG, DUNONG, SULONG PROGRAM: ITS IMPACT ON CAMPUS JOURNALISM PERFORMANCE OF A PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL IN SOUTHERN NUEVA VIZCAYA

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of the "Tulong, Dunong, Sulong Program: Campus Journalism" extension project of the College of Teacher Education of Nueva Vizcaya State University-Bambang Campus. The extension project spearheaded seminars and training to develop skills in campus journalism, such as news writing, feature writing, sports writing, editorial writing, editorial cartooning, photojournalism, and layouting. The beneficiaries were the students and teachers of a public secondary school in Southern Nueva Vizcaya. This mixed-method research utilizing the sequential explanatory design was aimed to explore the attainment of the objectives of the extension project, particularly its relevance and timeliness, its impact on other aspects of the beneficiaries, and its strengths and weaknesses. The data were gathered using the researcher-made quality assurance and measurement evaluation tool (quantitative), document scanning, and through a semi-structured interview (qualitative). Descriptive statistics and thematic analysis were used to analyze the strands of data. The 10 participants were purposively taken: two school paper advisers, three mentors/coaches, and five student journalists. All the training conducted were rated outstanding. Triangulated results showed that the extension project had contributed significantly based on the results of the press conferences participated. There were also improvements in other aspects of the beneficiaries, which were classified as increased productivity in publication, development of skills in journalistic writing, and improvement of academic achievement. The strengths and weaknesses of the project were also unveiled. For strengths, they were generally

classified as provided maximum experience, invited resource speakers/ materials, and cost-effective. Meanwhile, the weaknesses were generally identified as time management, delivery method, and pace and information absorption.

Keywords: *campus journalism, extension project, impact study, Tulong, Dunong, Sulong Program*

INTRODUCTION

Implementing extension programs and services is one of the means by which Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are directed to induce change in the members of their community. Being one of the premier universities in the Philippines, one of the thrusts of the Nueva Vizcaya State University is Research and Extension Programs. It includes in its general mandate to undertake extension service (RA 9402). Among the university's extension service modalities are programs or projects implemented for community stakeholders with the objective of fostering the development of skills for the efficient and effective transmission of knowledge.

As the pillar of social development, educational institutions have a social duty to strengthen communities and improve lives by transmitting knowledge and technology through training, workshops, seminars, and technical advisors (Codamon-Dugyon, 2016).

The College of Teacher Education (CTE) is one of the four colleges at NVSU-Bambang Campus that specifically targets clients in the education sector whose requirements align with the college's mission and priorities, such as Skills Training and Literacy. Campus journalism, which is related to skills training and literacy, is essential to each institution since it shapes students' abilities and talents in writing and assesses how well schools are able to compete with other institutions. In accordance with the university's mission to transform lives and the community and in response to requests for training and workshops on writing school papers, the CTE, together with The University Gazette, students and faculty of Bachelor of Secondary Education, Bachelor of Elementary Education, Master of Arts in Education, Master of Arts in Teaching, Master of Education in Science Education and Doctor of Education, planned to conduct a Campus Journalism Seminar-Workshop in conjunction with its extension project, "Tulong, Dunong, Sulong."

This project is a seminar and workshop on news writing, feature writing, sports writing, editorial writing and cartooning, photojournalism, and layouting that will give the school a great opportunity to begin establishing its school paper. Through the provision of pertinent services and suitable resources, this extension initiative aimed to engage the

academic community and maximize the potential of the targeted clientele, especially in the field of Campus Journalism.

The Campus Journalism Project was created to give secondary students in one public secondary school in Southern Nueva Vizcaya the necessary knowledge and abilities to produce a school newspaper. The training program covers the fundamentals of the various types of journalism writing.

The extension project started in 2018. The project has implemented training sessions. The training included News Writing, Feature Writing, Sports Writing, Editorial Writing, Editorial Cartooning, Photo Journalism, and Layout Design. Extensionists from the CTE were the trainers for the project. Others, who served as trainers, were invited experts who had created a name in the field of Campus Journalism. The project followed the methodology illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Project Methodology

Three years from its implementation and completion, an impact assessment of the project is beneficial to measure how the project transformed the lives of its beneficiaries. This impact assessment study will describe the point of view of the beneficiaries regarding the project and how the project has had a significant impact on their lives, specifically in their responsibilities as school paper advisers and mentors for the teachers and as campus journalists for the students.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the participants' level of evaluation of the extension project in terms of relevance and timeliness?
- 2) How is the student journalists' performance in the different areas of journalism since the conduct of the extension project?

3) What are the improvements since the conduct of the extension project on Campus Journalism?

4) What are the strengths and weaknesses of the extension project on Campus Journalism?

METHODOLOGY

The mixed-method research design was used in this study. The study is a sequential explanatory analysis of the impact of the extension project on Campus Journalism among student journalists and school paper advisers, mentors and coaches in a public secondary school in Southern Nueva Vizcaya. The participants were the two school paper advisers, three mentors/coaches, and five student journalists who attended the training sessions. Using purposive sampling, only 10 participants were considered because of the inclusion criteria set by the researcher: 1) must have attended the training; 2) is an active member of the school paper; 3) participated in press conferences; and 4) must be willing to participate in this study. Voluntary participation and consent were asked from the respondents. The anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses were guaranteed.

For the quantitative data analysis, the mean was used in the evaluation of the beneficiaries of the extension project (trainings/sessions). The data were gathered using the researcher-made quality assurance and measurement evaluation form. Document scanning was done to unveil the performances of the students in the different areas over the years. For the discussion of the impact and, strengths and weaknesses of the extension project, qualitative research was utilized. The data were gathered through a semi-structured interview. Three research experts and two English language teachers validated the instruments. Thematic analysis using the framework of Braun and Clarke (2022) was used in analyzing, interpreting, and presenting the qualitative data. Focus Group Discussion was also done to crystalize the data gathered.

In order to gather pertinent data, the researcher sought permission to perform the study by filing a formal request letter to the office of the School Principal. The researcher personally conducted the semi-structured interview when the request was approved. The purpose, aims, and significance of the research were explained to the participants before the interview proper. The participants were encouraged to be truthful in their responses to ensure the study's results and conclusions were reliable and valid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Training evaluation results of the extension project

Training Topics	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
News Writing	4.8	Outstanding
Feature Writing	4.9	Outstanding
Sports Writing	4.8	Outstanding
Editorial Writing	4.9	Outstanding
Editorial Cartooning	4.2	Very Satisfactory
Photojournalism	4.8	Outstanding
Layouting	4.1	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	4.64	Outstanding

Table 1. Training Evaluation Results Based on Relevance and Timeliness

The implementation of the Tulong, Dunong, Sulong Program on Campus Journalism was considered successful in attaining its objectives, as seen in the skills assessment of the students after each workshop. Among the journalism skills shown in Table 1, Feature Writing and Editorial writing got the highest evaluation with an average weighted mean of 4.9. These are followed by News Writing, Sports Writing, and Photojournalism, with 4.8 weighted mean. Editorial Cartooning got a 4.2 mean. The lowest is Layout Design, with a mean of 4.1. Nevertheless, all of the tracks got a verbal interpretation of Outstanding.

The results would mean that the beneficiaries considered the training as effective. The results also imply that the extension project led to the acquisition of different campus journalism skills. This was because of the effective program management, delivery of content based on the learning needs, alignment of training with the objectives of the extension project, effective training measurement and relevant training content, and effective reinforcement of training to increase learning retention.

As support, Fonseca (2018) emphasized that campus journalism workshops, such as the extension project, provide students with the opportunity to refine and practice their journalistic skills, as well as be the voice of change by getting readers to think about pressing issues that they might not have read about elsewhere.

2. Performance of the school in the different areas of journalism during the three-year Division Schools Press Conference (DSPC)

Student Beneficiary	Category	Place	Year
Student A	Feature Writing	Unplaced 2 nd 3 rd	2019-2020 2020-2021 2021-2022
Student B	News Writing	Unplaced 6 th 4 th	2019-2020 2020-2021 2021-2022
Student C	Editorial Writing	7 th 4 th 2 nd	2019-2020 2020-2021 2021-2022
Student D	Photojournalism	Unplaced 4 th 3 rd	2019-2020 2020-2021 2021-2022

Table 2. Results of Division Schools Press Conference

After the project was launched in 2018, students participated in different areas of journalism during Division Schools Press Conferences (DSPCs).

In terms of the specific skills acquired by the students, the table shows that four students have significant acquisitions, as seen in the three-year press conferences. Student A, from being unplaced in 2019-2020, he garnered ^{second} place in 2020-2021 and ^{third} place in 2021-2022. Student B also improved in News Writing from being unplaced in 2019-2020 to ^{sixth} place in 2020-2021 and ^{fourth} place in 2021-2022. Meanwhile, Student C went from ^{seventh} place in 2019-2020, ^{fourth} place in 2020-2021, to ^{second} place in 2021-2022 in Editorial Writing. In Photojournalism, Student D was unplaced in 2019-2020, ^{fourth} place in 2020-2021, and ^{third} place in 2021-2022.

The results imply that the training was effective in teaching the students the necessary skills. It equipped them with the content and ability to produce quality journalistic articles. The extension project also prepared the students and even the teachers who act as coaches to writing competitions such as the Division Schools Press Conference which is done every academic year in the Basic Education.

Chavez's study (2023) provided evidence that extension programs in campus journalism really help mold student journalists. The primary reason is that the students

are not only exposed to the content (mechanics and/or conventions in journalistic writing) but also trained to write and produce journalistic articles.

3. Improvements since the conduct of the extension project on Campus Journalism

The following improvements have occurred since the conduct of the extension project on Campus Journalism, which was generally classified as increased productivity in publication, development of skills in journalistic writing, and improvement of academic achievement.

Increased productivity in publication. This category appeared the most frequent in the responses of the participants. The participants perceived that because of the extension project on Campus Journalism, the writing, layouting, and production of school papers became more manageable since the writers, artists, and advisers were given input that enabled them to perform their duties and responsibilities even more effectively. These are some of the responses from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

“Based on my observation, they submit more articles and cartoon,” (P2)
“...because of the training, the student-journalists, especially the writers produce more articles,” (P4)
"Mas dumami po yung inspiration namin to write and mas madali nalang yung pagsusulat naming ng mga articles." (Our inspiration to write increased, and it was easier for us to write articles.) (P8)

The extension project was believed to have given the participants a forum for academic conversation where detailed suggestions were openly offered via the experiences of the speakers, and specific inquiries were answered. As a result, following the discussion, the seminar-workshops allowed participants an opportunity to put the ideas into practice. The seminar-workshop gave the participants a constructivist perspective where they could practice and produce more articles ready for publication, hence, making the publication more productive.

Similar to the findings of Dela Rosa et al. (2021), the participants expressed consensus on the positive impact of participating in campus publications or undergoing school journalism training on their proficiency in their respective areas of expertise, such as writing, editing, and visual communication, when compared to their previous abilities.

Development of skills in journalistic writing. Appearing to be less frequent, this category is an improvement among student journalists after engaging in the training on Campus Journalism. This became evident because of the number of journalistic works submitted to the editors and school paper advisers. During the pre-press conferences conducted in school, the advisers and coaches observed the improvement of the student

journalists in their style of writing their articles. The students' critical understanding of the mechanics and rules in writing in their respective fields was noticeable in their outputs. Here are a few of the answers from the participants who took part (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"The students gained more knowledge in their respective fields," (P1)

"Nung nagtraining kami before the contest, napansin ko ang development ng mga outputs niya," (When we trained before the contest, I noticed the development of his outputs) (P5)

"I think I improved po lalo na sa pagsunod sa rules in writing the article," (I think I improved especially in following the rules in writing the article) (P10)

The participants believed that because of their experience during the training, their skills have improved. The extension project on Campus Journalism helped the student-journalists to experience first-hand not only the sharing of the resource speakers but especially the writing process following the suggested writing conventions. Henceforth, experiential learning is an appropriate learning strategy, and journalism instruction is in fact, using it more often (Berger & Foote, 2017).

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, the training was still made possible using technologies and online platforms. In fact, it served as a new learning among journalists since technology became a medium during conferences. A wide range of technological resources that journalists may use in their professional practices to make their work more accessible to their viewers best describes this period (Veglis & Maniou, 2019).

The study of Albino (2021) also revealed that the five-day Campus Journalism training conducted in a secondary national high school in Subic, Philippines, improved the students' writing skills. This was manifested through the improvement of the school paper and the students' performances in press conferences.

Improvement of academic achievement. This category was the least often mentioned in the participants' responses. Participants believed that because of the training, not only that they improve their skills in writing articles, but they also improved in terms of their performance in their academics, particularly in the English subject. Not because students were given extra credits but because of the essays and other outputs submitted to the teachers. Here are a few of the remarks from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

“Based sa sabi ng co-teacher ko, mas gumaling daw siya when it comes to writing essays.” (Based on what my co-teacher had mentioned, he said that he got better when it comes to writing essays.) (P1)

“As her teacher in English, I’ve seen her improvement in the subject.” (P7)

“Tumaas rin po ang aking mga grades kasi nakakarelate po ako hindi lang sa pagsusulat kundi pati sa mga nangyayari around us since we need to watch news and be aware of the issues,” (My grades also increased because I can relate not only to writing but also to what is happening around us since we need to watch news and be aware of the issues,) (P9)

More than just a curricular activity, the participants believed that attending press conferences and trainings on Campus Journalism helped them improve their academic performance—writing in English and keeping up with the latest news or issues in Araling Panlipunan, for instance. Bilinovich (2022) emphasized that student journalism may serve as a model for the actual world by allowing students to freely and openly explore ideas, debate, and identify issues that need to be addressed.

Furthermore, these campus journalists are young people who will soon become adults and who are developing their maturity, ideas, philosophies, academic success, and identities (Make My News, 2017). More importantly, though, they could already be agents of change in the communities they belong as a result of training like the extension on campus journalism (Cortes, 2014).

4. Strengths and weaknesses of the extension project on Campus Journalism

The following are the strengths and weaknesses of the conducted extension project on Campus Journalism. The strengths were generally classified as provided maximum experience, invited resource speakers/ materials, and cost-effective. Meanwhile, the weaknesses were generally identified as time management, delivery method, and pace and information absorption.

Provided maximum experience. This category appeared the most frequently in the responses of the participants when asked about the strengths of the extension project on Campus Journalism. They believed that because of the extension project on Campus Journalism, the students gained more ideas through the maximum experience provided by the resource speakers. Students also were given opportunities to apply the concepts shared with them. The student-journalists, according to the participants, underwent a series of writing wherein their outputs were checked every after a writing session. Here

are a few of the remarks from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"The workshops provided the students time to practice their field." (P1)
"...and it provided them actual experience." (P4)
"Yung trainings po ay nagbigay sa amin ng experience para ipractice yung sasalihan namin." (The trainings gave us the experience to practice what we will be participating in.) (P8)

The responses imply that the project provided the participants with experiences where theories and concepts could be applied, especially in writing their articles. It is also understandable that the extension project provided not only concepts in journalistic writing but also training or activities where students could deepen their understanding of the conventions and mechanics of writing in their respective fields.

This is supported by Loveland's study (2014), which discovered that action-based instruction (including seminars and workshops) increased students' understanding and procedural activity in planning and logistical abilities. On this basis, students also had the chance to comprehend and put their writing styles into practice.

Invited resource speakers/materials. This category was also frequent in the remarks from the participants. In the interview, the participants explained that most of the speakers were really experts in their respective fields. Some of them joined press conferences before and made a mark by winning and bagging awards. Some speakers are part of organizations related to journalism/ campus journalism. Here are a few of the responses from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"The speakers are really expert in their field." (P1)
"...we are also thankful for the PPT's given because it helps us go back with the content," (P3)
"...gusto rin po naming yung presentations kasi ibinigay po para po may additional reference kami aside from the book." (We also like the presentations because they are given so that we have additional references aside from the book.) (P9)

It can be understood that the speakers are effective in teaching the concepts and in giving tips and techniques. The materials used are informative and helpful references for the students. Kurtus (2022) underlined that a speaker with insufficient knowledge needs to learn what he or she is talking about and how to create a successful presentation since being effective implies being well-informed and educated about the ideas in journalism. Knowing the material and successfully communicating it are both characteristics of good speakers.

Cost-effective. This category also appeared in the responses of the participants, albeit least frequently. It was mentioned because the training on Campus Journalism was an extension program between the two institutions; therefore, there is no need to spend the professional fee of the resource speakers. Compared to other training or seminars conducted in school, this training was not costly because most of the expenses were mostly operating expenses. The school publication should have spent more considering the number of sessions, training, and impact it gave to the beneficiaries. Here are a few of the answers from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"The school doesn't have to pay much anymore for the trainings," (P2)

"...we only have to provide snacks and lunch since the speakers were only given certificates and tokens. The project helped the school and particularly the publication to save some funds." (P4)

"Ang maganda pa po ay hindi kami gumastos para sa trainings. Nung nagpatutor po kasi ako is may bayad." (The good thing is that we did not spend for training. When I was tutored, there was a fee.) (P10)

According to Molaba (2023), engaging in thorough training programs that are continuous is crucial for realizing one's full potential. However, the extension project made better use of already available resources reduced the need for outside trainers, and saved a significant amount of publication expenditures while students learned practical skills that were essential to their fields and positions, which cut down on the price of formal training programs.

Time management. This category was the most frequent when the participants were asked during the interview about the weaknesses of the extension project. It was a weakness since most of the speakers also had to attend to their jobs. The student journalists also have to prioritize their academics aside from their writing or training sessions. In the interview, finding the perfect time that would fit the schedule of the students and the resource speakers was really a struggle. Nonetheless, most of the sessions were still done after work hours and classes. Here are a few of the remarks from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"Naging problem ang scheduling ng trainings kasi yung mga bata also need to go home after classes. If maaga naman, the speakers also have work to attend." (The scheduling of trainings became a problem because the children also need to go home after classes. If it is early, the speakers also have work to attend.) (P3)

"Sinusundo nalang po ako nila mama pero nagagabihan po ako noon," (They were picking me up, but I sometimes go home late.) (P8)

The responses suggest the necessity to build up schedules if there are additional training since students and resource speakers also have obligations to attend. The remarks also imply that practice and learning take time, especially when it comes to journalism. Effective time management may transform a training program into an extremely productive, outstanding procedure. More and better learning occurs when time is more efficiently managed (Webmaster, 2010). Just-in-time training helps students retain their knowledge and find solutions when they need them by saving time, reclaiming time, and spending time wisely.

Delivery method. This category was also disclosed as a weakness. According to the participants, during the pandemic, trainings such as this were really hard to attend, especially for students who have little to no knowledge of using technology. Though it served as a new learning among the students, the platform was still an obstacle they had to go through during the conduct of the sessions. Here are a few of the responses from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"Not all of the students have access to internet," (P1)

"Hindi po ako masyadong marunong gumamit ng google meet," (I don't know how to use google meet very well.) (P7)

According to Andriotis (2016), one more issue with training and development is making sure that your participants are completely engaged with your learning platform and material. In the delivery of the extension project, technology became a challenge among the students since most of them, though exposed to technologies, have little knowledge of how to use the applications or platform.

Pace and information absorption. This category was unveiled but the least frequent as a weakness of the extension project on Campus Journalism. Some of the lectures are delivered only in an hour. The pace of some of the training could have been faster since there were problems when it came to scheduling the students and speakers. In the interview, it was mentioned that since there were problems with the training hours, there was a need to fast-track the lectures and the students needed help in trying to understand and absorb all of the contents. Here are a few of the answers from the participants (*P refers to the participant; language use was retained to ascertain the authenticity of the responses given*):

"Medyo nagkaproblema sa bilis. Because the students were not met during a particular time, nagrurush na kung minsan para maideliver yung kailangan ituro." (I had a bit of a speed problem. Because the students were not met during a particular time, sometimes there was a rush to deliver what needed to be taught.) (P6)

“...nahirapan po ako sa pag-aral kasi bukod sa bago yung ibang techniques, medyo abrupt din po kung minsan ang training, pero okay parin naman po,” (I had a hard time studying because apart from the new techniques, the training was also a bit abrupt at times, but it's still okay.) (P10)

The responses imply the need to consider the time of both the speakers and the students. That is, the content must be delivered on time, and the students must be able to understand it and apply it during training or competitions.

Conclusions

1. The training conducted was rated outstanding. Triangulated results showed that the extension project contributed significantly based on the results of the press conferences participated.

2. The beneficiaries improved in other aspects. Generally, the improvements were classified as increased productivity in publication, development of skills in journalistic writing, and improvement of academic achievement.

3. The strengths of the extension project were generally classified as: provided maximum experience, invited resource speakers/ materials, and cost-effective.

4. The extension project's weaknesses were generally identified as time management, delivery method, and pace and information absorption.

Recommendations

1. Because the training was all rated outstanding and there is considerable improvement based on the competition results and other aspects of the beneficiaries, it is recommended that the project be replicated in a new location and with a larger number of beneficiaries.

2. To solve the deficiencies, the extension leaders may consider consistency and adaptability, a comprehensive grasp of the seminar-workshop process, and the inclusion of all participants in the decision-making process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a declaration that the author sought the approval of the authority before the conduct of the study. Only the willing participants were involved in this research. Voluntary participation and signed informed consent were asked from the participants. Though audit trails/interview logs were utilized, their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses were guaranteed. No conflict of interest exists.

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